

DEFENDING INDONESIA'S ENVIRONMENT: AN ECOLOGICAL POLITICAL ANALYSIS OF CHANGE.ORG ONLINE PETITIONS FROM 2015 TO 2022

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Abstract

This research explores the impact of digital democracy on Change.org online petitions. These petitions contribute to efforts aimed at addressing environmental damage by influencing individual community behavior or shaping environmental and natural resource governance policies. The methodology involves categorizing data into local, national, and global environmental themes on Change.org. The validation process includes assessing digital activism elements, such as discussions and the spread of meme propaganda, through the selection of petitions to consolidate data. Additionally, media analysis is employed to observe reactions and thematic interactions on platforms such as Twitter and national-international media websites. The study suggests that digital democracy has heightened environmental awareness and defense over the past decade. Another key finding is the ability of online petitions, through social media interactions, to impact policies or induce policy changes for at least ten years. However, successful awareness-raising in digital media and the ability to compel stakeholders to make a significant impact require certain prerequisites. Hundreds of environmental petitions on Change.org have significantly influenced project cancellations, trials, the criminalization of corporations by law enforcement agencies, and the postponement or cancellation of specific development programs

Keywords: Change.org, Digital Democracy, Ecology Development, Petition

INTRODUCTION

In response to environmental challenges, individuals are increasingly participating in various activities, such as massive street protests and environmental protection campaigns. These actions are fueled by advancements in technology and knowledge. The scope of environmental issues is vast, encompassing concerns like air and water pollution, illegal logging, forest fires, water scarcity, soil degradation, climate change, and the illegal sale of protected wildlife. Addressing these challenges necessitates a fundamental shift in our approach to the environment. It requires fostering public awareness of the ecological situation and cultivating an attitude that recognizes the interconnectedness of all life—humans, plants, animals, and the universe. While environmental damage signals existing ecological awareness, there is a need for more precision, depth, and comprehensive understanding.

Recognizing the power of public engagement, activists and individuals passionate about environmental issues can explore alternative platforms beyond social media. One such platform is Change.org, a website that hosts online petitions addressing a wide range of concerns, including environmental issues. Online petitions serve as a method of political engagement, connecting people directly with the government.

The significance of platforms like Change.org is amplified by the global reach of the internet. In Indonesia, where internet usage reached 76.8 percent of the population by March 2021, online petitions provide a powerful tool for civic participation (Katadata.co.id, 2021). Change.org offers country-specific versions for Southeast Asian nations, including Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Singapore, the Philippines, and Vietnam. These localized platforms address petitions relevant to each country's unique setting and issues.

Change.org's impact is evident in Indonesia, where the digital movement on the platform has steadily grown from 2012 to 2020, as indicated by website data (Table 1). The platform's availability in multiple languages, including Indonesian, and the presence of local teams in 18 nations further enhance its effectiveness as a tool for mobilizing public support and advocating for environmental change (Change.org, 2019).

Table 1. Number of Change.org Indonesia Petition Users

Year	Number of Users
2012	130.000
2013	390.000
2014	900.000
2015	1.900.000
2016	3.130.000
2017	4.060.000
2018	6.500.000
2019	13.300.000
2020	16.300.000

Source: (Change.org, 2021).

The table above illustrates the growing utilization of the Change.org digital platform by Indonesians, spanning the leadership periods of Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono to Joko Widodo. Notably, the platform's user base experienced a substantial increase starting in 2017, with projections indicating over 16 million users by the end of 2020—a noteworthy surge of 3 million from the preceding year. In Southeast Asia, Indonesia stands out as the country with the highest number of Change.org users, with a significant year-over-year increase attributed to its extensive internet user population.

Thailand, alongside Indonesia, emerges as one of the most active online petitioners, particularly on the Change.org platform. Statistics reveal that in 2018, Indonesian users submitted 5,410,783 petitions, while Thailand recorded 2,872,780 petitions the following year. The trend continues in 2019, with Indonesia leading with 10,410,717 petition submissions and Thailand following closely with 3,541,564. This dominance underscores Indonesia's position as the country with the most Change.org users, a testament to its thriving digital community (Change.org, 2018a, 2019).

The high internet penetration rate in Indonesia facilitates the convergence of social media and policy advocacy, as observed in the Digital Opinion Movement (DMO). This movement, influenced by technological evolution and social media dynamics, creates a virtual network where individuals freely express their opinions, contributing to a collaborative effort in altering specific policies. The migration of political engagement from physical to digital spaces, exemplified by platforms like Change.org, signifies a transformative shift in political activism (Barisione & Michailidou, 2017).

Online petitions, as seen on platforms like Change.org, have become powerful tools for influencing social and political change. They leverage textual research to effectively indoctrinate targets and potential supporters, incorporating cognitive, emotional, and moral components into the petition language (Chen et al., 2019).. In Indonesia, the success of online petitions, particularly those addressing environmental concerns, reflects the population's heightened awareness of climate change issues.

The success of online petitions in Indonesia reflects the concerns of the people regarding environmental issues. Mass media plays a crucial role in facilitating public comprehension of these concerns. The emergence of new media has increased public understanding of the dynamics of environmental harm, making it easier for individuals to support social movements. Change.org, in particular, has documented a significant increase in public engagement and enthusiasm on the issue of climate change from 2015 to 2020. Environmental petitions consistently ranked among the top five most popular themes, with climate change being a central focus in one-third of the petitions. With 730,964 signatures, environmental issues became the most popular petition category on Change.org.

To put this into perspective, cyber-activism, described as citizen-driven civic engagement, aims to construct a more open, transparent, and interactive society (Pérez-Escolar et al., 2020). This paradigm of civic empowerment fulfills the communication demands of global users and is intertwined with the impact of globalization, technology, and the rapid expansion of communication networks. A study conducted by Halpern and Gibbs emphasize the role of social media as a catalyst for online debate, influencing the nature and content of online deliberation based on the type and structure of social platforms (Halpern & Gibbs, 2013).

Despite the positive aspects of social media in fostering democratic discourse, group solidarity, and creativity, there are challenges. Social media spaces resist transformation into physical political activism, creating conflicting power dynamics (Gukurume, 2017). In Myanmar, the failure to understand and mitigate risks associated with social media platforms left them vulnerable to abuse and weaponization. Examining how weaponized social media platforms responded to crises can provide insights for mitigating future threats effectively (Rio, 2021).

The paper argues that the Internet, specifically the World Wide Web, presents an opportunity for civic engagement through various means such as E-voting, E-government tools, and online public debates. The potential for the Internet to generate an online public conversation that empowers citizens (Amichai-hamburger & Mckenna, 2008). The authors aim to contribute to the literature on digital democracy and environmental concerns by exploring how digital

democracy, particularly through e-petitions, can be leveraged. The study focuses on a specific scenario involving environmental issues and the use of Change.org petitions from 2015 to 2022 in Indonesia, providing valuable insights into the intersection of digital democracy and environmental activism.

METHOD

This study is based on the concept of political participation - a digital environment understood as actions taken by individual members. The authors used petition mapping taken from the Change.org online platform. This research employs qualitative methods, a subfield of social science that helps researchers interpret and comprehend experiences or social realities. (Kumar, 2018). This study employs multiple evidence sources to describe the modern phenomenon around the Change.org petition. In this study, the Change.org petition phenomenon is examined through the lens of political-environmental issues in Indonesia from 2015 to 2022 (Ozkan, 2004).

This study presents an assessment of 100 cases of environmental petitions and their impact on Indonesian democracy from 2015 to 2022 that were published and disseminated on the Change.org petition website, then from 100 petitions, the authors divided into three petition clusters as shown in the following table:

Table 2. 100 Cases of Petitions on Change.org

Rejection	Management	Protection	
KLHK Tolak Persetujuan Lingkungan Indonesia Dairi Prima (2022)	Tolak Tambang Batu Bara di Hulu Sungai Tengah (2018)	Bebaskan Selat Madura Dari Mikro plastik (2021)	Stop Jual Beli Bagian Tubuh Satwa Di Lindungi (2022)
Tolak Kereta Gantung Rinjani (2022)	Stop Tipu Daya Atas Nama Konservasi, Tolak Pembangunan di Pulau Komodo (2018)	Pengurangan Pemakaian Plastik di Indonesia (2021)	Indonesia Darurat Polusi, Gubernur Indonesia Sahkan Pergub Udara Bersih Secepatnya (2022)
Selamatkan Kopi Gayo, Tolak Tambang Linge (2022)	Segara Hentikan Proyek PLTA Batang Toru (2018)	Berikan Opsi Kemasan Minim Plastik Sekali Pakai (2021)	Jangan BOM Wakatobi (2022)
Bank BCA, Hentikan Berharap Pada Batu Bara	Tolak Pembangunan Panas Bumi di Gunung Talang: Stop Kekerasan & Kriminalisasi Masyarakat (2018)	Uniqlo, H&M, Zara dan Adidas, Apa Kabar Program Peduli Lingkunganmu? (2021)	Save Kali Progo (2022)
Tolak Pengkondisian Penyadapan Getah Pinus di Kawasan Taman Nasional Gunung Ciremai (2022)	Tolak Gugatan Terhadap Basuki Wasis Pejuang Lingkungan (2018)	Bebaskan Bengawan Solo Dari Mikro plastik, Sebelum Terlambat (2020)	Selamatkan Hutan Kemenyan Di Humbahas Miliki Masyarakat Adat Pergamanan Bintang Maria (2022)

Hentikan Rencana Pertambangan Batuan Andesit d Desa Wadas (2021)	Tolak Tambang Indonesia Emas Mineral Murni Di Nagan Raya dan Aceh Tenggara Provinsi Aceh (2018)	Bebaskan Sungai Brantas dari Mikro plastik Sebelum Terlambat (2020)	Pak Yaqut, Sama – Sama Jadikan Masjid Ramah Lingkungan dan Irit Air Tanah (2021)
Usut Pengelolaan Limbah Indonesia Toba Pulp Lestari di Parbulu (2021)	Batalkan Proyek PLTA Tampur yang Menngancam Jutaan Jiwa (2018)	Clean Up & Pulihkan Bumi Jawa Timur dari Timbunan Limbah Bahan Berbahaya Beracun (2020)	Indonesia, Tangani Krisis Iklim dan Targetkan Net-Zero Emissions Tahun 2050 (2021)
Selamatkan Hutan Adat Baduy, Selamatkan Kawasan Hulu Sungai Ciujung (2021)	Tolak Tambang Batubara di Seblat (2018)	Stop Galon Sekali Pakai (2020)	Pak Nadiem, Selamatkan Kami Dengan Pendidikan Iklim (2021)
Masyarakat Adat Rendu, Ndora dan Lambo Tolak Lokasi Pembangunan Waduk Lambo (2021)	Tolak Kehadiran Tambang Emas Silo (2018)	Segera Terbitkan Peraturan Cukai Kantong Plastik (2018)	Krisis Iklim Indonesia Makin Parah, G20 Bisa Apa?, Deklarasi Darurat Iklim Segara (2021)
Sangihe Pulau yang Indah, Kami Tolak Tambang (2021)	Desak Mahkamah Agung Perintahkan Meulaboh Untuk Eksekusi Perusahaan Pembakar Lahan (2018)	Go-Jek, Sediakan Pilihan untuk Sertakan Alat Makan Sekali Pakai (2018)	Selamatkan Sungai Malili (2021)
Dukung Bupati Soroang Bela Masyarakat Adat Lawan Perusahaan Kelapa Sawit di Indonesia Jayapura (2021)	Hentikan Obral Izin Tambang Untuk Kampanye Politik (2018)	Pengelolaan Limbah Medis Harus Transparan, Cepat dan Ramah Lingkungan (2018)	Kami Mau #UdaraBersihSekarang, Segera Implementasi Putusan CLS Pencemaran Udara Indonesia (2021)
Tolak Tambang Bontocani (2021)	Tolak Kebun Hancurkan Tanah Adat Kami di Kebar, Tambrau, Papua Barat (2017)	Hentikan Epidemik Plastik di Supermarket (2018)	Selamatkan Hutan Gunung Lawu (2020)
Stop Pembangunan Hotel Manado Eco Family Selamatkan Masyarakat Papatungan Minut (2021)	Gubernur Indonesia Stop Proyek Reklamasi Pantai Utara Indonesia (2017)	Budayakan Kumpulkan & Pilah Sampah Plastik Hindari Pencemaran Lingkungan (2019)	Save Raja Ampat's Reefs from Overtouris (2020)
Hakim MK, Batalkan Aturan Mineral Batu Bara untuk Melindungi Hak Warga Memperoleh Lingkungan yang Sehat (2021)	Indonesia Tolak Reklamasi (2017)	Wali Kota Malang: Keluarkan Peraturan Daerah Larangan Penggunaan Kantong Plastik (2019)	Komodo Juga Hewan yang Hampir Punah (2020).
Tolak Pertambangan Ilegal di Sebulu Kutai Kartanegara (2020)	Stop Tambang Emas Si Junjung, Selamatkan Lingkungan (2017)	Asosiasi Daur Ulang Plastik: Stop Uji Materi Plastik Sekali Pakai di Bali (2019)	Stop Bakar Sampah, Kembalikan Langit Biru Indonesia (2020)

Stop Danai PLTU Indramayu Baru. PLTU Bukan Untuk Masyarakat (2020)	Tolak Pabrik Semen di Rembang (2017)	Sudah Saatnya Sedotan Plastik Dikurangi (2019)	Selamatkan Batang Tori dan Orang utan Terlangka Di Dunia (2019)
Hentikan Proyek Food Estate di Indonesia Tengah (2020)	Save Laun Belitung, Tolak Penambangan Timah Di Perairan Belitung (2017)	Indonesia Bukan Tempat Sampah Dunia (2019)	#JokowiLihatKaletng Kabut Semakin Parah, Kami Minta Tindak Lanjutnya (2019)
Hentikan Operasi Indonesia SML di Hutan Adat Laman Kinipan (2020)	Tolak Tambang Mangan di Pulau Sabu (2017)		Tinjau Ulang ! RUU Pertanahan Belum Layak untuk Disahkan @DPR_RI (2019)
Batalkan Regulasi yang Dorong Kehancuran Hutan (2020)	Hilangkan Tambang Ilegal di Muratara (2017)		Selamatkan Terumbu Karang di Lokasi Pelita Pasir Putih Situbondo (2018)
Cabut Izin PLTYU Ombilin di Sawahlunto (2019)	Melawan Banjir, Melawan Kekerasan (2017)		Gunung Bulu Bawakaraeng Harus Di Heritage (2018)
Tutup Keramba Perusahaan Budidaya Perikanan di Danau Toba (2019)	Stop Pembangunan Resort di Telaga Warna Puncak (2017)		Kembalikan Ulin & Tumbuhan Langkah Lain Ke Daftar Dilindungi (2019)
Tolak Tambang Batu Bara Perusahaan Buana Tambang Jaya Kabupaten Kampar, Riau (2019)	Pak @jokowi, Cabut Izin PLTP Baturaden (2017)		Selamatkan Sumber Air Indonesia Timur (2019)
Tolak Tambang Andesit Krendetan (2019)	Pemerintah Sukoharjo: Pindahkan/Tutup Indonesia. RUM Limbah Mencemari Udara Merusak Ekosistem (2017)		Jowoki Tunaikan Janji Indonesia Untuk Hilangkan Asap Di Riau (2019)
Tolak Penambangan Kali Gendol (2019)	Batalkan SK Reklamasi Pulau G Demi Nelayan (2016)		Lepaskan Penyus dan Hiu, Sekarang (2016)
Tolak Transmigrasi ke Indonesia Tengah (2019)	Tolak Pembangunan Apartemen M Icon di Sleman Indonesia (2015)		Ayo Dukung Revolusi Energi (2016)
Hukum Perusahaan Pembakaran Hutan dan Lahan di Riau (2019)	Cabut Izin Perusahaan Dari Hutan Sepa (2015)		Jangan Rusak Hutan Terakhir Kami (2015)
Cabut Izin Perusahaan Pembakar Lahan (2019)	Tutup dan Hukum Perusahaan Lubang Tambang Batu Bara Samarinda yang Membunuh Anak – Anak (2015)		Bantu Kami Menyelamatkan Laut (2015)

Masyarakat Dayak
Menolak Program
Transmigrasi (2019)

Hentikan Asap Racun
Tahunan di Riau (2015)

Source: Collected and Proceeded by the Authors

This research required 100 petitions because the authors completed an early phase concerning the study of digital democracy and people's aspirations for ecological politics through digital democracy. Change.org.

Table 3. Petition Clusters and Petition Cluster Explanations

Petition Clusters	Petition Cluster Explanation
Rejection	The themes of the petition clusters include rejection of development, and rejection of exploitation of environmental damage caused by industrial companies.
Management	The specifications of this petition cluster are related to ecosystem management, such as plastic waste management and plastic use reduction.
Protection	Clusters are based on river, mountain, and animal protection.

Source: Collected and Proceeded by the Authors

Among the one hundred petitions relating to ecological politics and environmental protection, three groups frequently arise. There are three clusters of environmental rejection, management, and protection. The research also assesses petitions that were successful and those that were unsuccessful. Several criteria were used to select the petitions that were analyzed, including the petition's success in attracting media attention or obtaining media coverage, the petition's involvement of specific communities/organizations or community groups, and the petition's success in mobilizing other activities supporting policy advocacy outcomes.

The researcher then picked petitions that were still in progress or had not yet succeeded in producing narrative appeal material for multiple levels of success and procedures from the first 100 petitions. After sifting through 100 petitions, the researcher formulated four indicators that would be reviewed in the debate, including Petition Information, Petition Dialogue, Monitoring, and Petition Decision Making.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Digital Democracy as a Theoretical Framework

Typically, digital democracy or e-Democracy is viewed as a three-dimensional notion (see Figure. 1). These elements are directly related to the fundamental requirements for utilizing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in democratic nations. The basic requirements mentioned are the most important prerequisites for creating and implementing e-Democracy.

Access to digital media (capable infrastructure) comes first, followed by internet freedom and the regulation of legal rules governing internet use and content access. Equally essential are legal protections governing internet access, such as filtering or banning by regulatory organizations.

Figure 1. Three Dimensions of the e-Democracy Concept

Source: (Kneuer, 2016)

E-participation represents the second dimension of digital democracy, encompassing three primary variations in decision-making within the realm of e-democracy. Specifically, e-Participation employs both a 'bottom-up' and 'top-down' approach (Coleman & Blumler, 2009). In a different context and dimension, e-voting stands out as a distinct process in decision-making, functionally different from e-participation. The role of digital media as a new societal medium should be acknowledged for its significance as both a source of knowledge and a monitoring tool in contemporary society. Consequently, the incorporation of e-monitoring into the digital democracy dimension becomes essential (Hindman, 2009). Citizens can actively monitor government operations through e-monitoring tools, akin to the parliamentary watch model established in Germany to hold Members of Parliament (MPs) accountable. E-participation, as a concept, encompasses four fundamental levels: e-information, e-consultation, e-monitoring, and decision-making. These participation levels reflect variances in time, effort, and commitment. Citizens can choose to use digital media for obtaining information or engaging in conversations with politicians through their official social media or email. Moreover, direct involvement in monitoring politicians is possible through specific platforms or by demanding participation in decisions, such as through e-petitions, success teams, and collaborative governance. For a visual representation of the public participation levels, please refer to Figure 2 on the next page.

Figure 2. e-Participation Level Indicators

E-participation		
Top-down	Levels of e-participation	Bottom-up
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites • Archived information (documents, data, etc.) 	Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blogs by citizens (not journalists or politicians that attract (national) public attention)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online consultation • Chatrooms • Online citizen juries 	Dialogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hashtags • Frequently asked questions use on websites of ministries, etc. • Emails, posts on websites of government members, members of parliament (MPs), etc. • Following government members, MPs, etc. on Facebook
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online surveys/polls • Participatory budgets • Collaborative governance • E-referenda/online voting tools* 	Monitoring Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online parliamentary monitoring • E-petitions • E-referendum initiative • Signing up to online campaigns

Source: (Kneuer, 2016)

In addition to e-Participation, which prioritizes the two factors, e-Government is an important aspect of digital democracy. In contrast to e-Participation, e-Government seeks to build public confidence in effective public services and policy implementation (Clift, 2004). Consequently, e-Government has the potential to enhance the quality of democracy in Indonesia. Based on the preceding arguments, it is possible to conclude that the description of the three aspects of digital democracy (free and equal access, e-Participation, and e-Government) can have an impact on the quality of democracy in Indonesia. Nevertheless, based on the current study, the author will focus on e-participation with a bottom-up approach as an analysis of the impact of online petitions on democracy and social movements in Indonesia, particularly politics to protect the environment, by analyzing data from the Change.org online petition website from 2015 to 2022.

Social media is an easily accessible platform because it can be opened, and social media is a feature that allows sharing and exchanging information. Consequently, its function can positively influence consumers and is a key source of behavior-based happiness (Tandon et al., 2021). The pervasiveness of social media in our lives necessitates the development of new skills and innovations for social media success (Pekkala & van Zoonen, 2021).

Change.org was established in 2007 as a charitable social network and project-based donating platform. It is the largest and most popular petition site, with more than 70 million users

in 196 countries, and is extensively embraced by social movement organizations working on a variety of causes (Huang et al., 2015). Change.org started in June 2012 in Indonesia with a mechanism for collecting signatures and opinions via digital social networks; each support received would send the petition to the email of the party to whom the petition is directed. The largest petition platform in the world empowers anyone, anywhere, to impact change. (Sukmi, 2015). This petition employs basic, plain language so that it can be easily comprehended by the use of neutral language (Kustriana, 2020). A revolutionary environmental movement shows unconsidered historical factors and elements involved in societal conflicts (Clark, 2002).

2. Information and Dialogue Petition

Information dissemination is an essential component that must be addressed when assessing e-participation and its impact on democracy. The emergence and virality of petitions contribute to disseminating information on contentious matters. Therefore, the authors utilize the Change.org petition website, which is extensively utilized by people worldwide, including Indonesia. Through the Change.org website, researchers evaluated the submitted information until the petition's whole discourse was shown. The author states that all 100 petitions on environmental protection in Indonesia, which are organized into three clusters titled "rejection," "management," and "protection," contain information and descriptions pertaining to environmental problems currently facing the community. As an example, related to the petition "KLHK Rejects PT Dairi Prima's Indonesian Environmental Approval" created by Monica Nauli Siregar on behalf of the Dairi people, the author discovered on the Change.org website a detailed explanation of environmental issues and the petition's goal (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Petition Information "KLHK Rejects PT Dairi Prima's Indonesia Environmental Approval" on the Change.org Website.

Kepada yang terhormat, Bapak Presiden RI, Joko Widodo dan Ibu Menteri Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan RI

Kami warga Dairi yang berada di wilayah disekitar PT DPM (Dairi Prima Mineral). Pada Oktober 2019 kami membuat pengaduan ke CAO (Compliance Advisor Ombudsman) badan kepatuhan independen yang mengawasi IFC (International Finance Corporation (IFC) dan MIGA yang merupakan bagian dari Bank Dunia

Sebagai warga masyarakat yang berpotensi terdampak atas rencana tambang PT. DPM, kami mengadu kepada CAO karena pendanaan penambangan tersebut disokong oleh IFC dan pengaduan kami diterima serta diproses.

Setelah penantian panjang kami, akhirnya pada awal Juli 2022, kami mendapatkan Laporan CAO yang merupakan hasil penilaian atas pengaduan yang kami lakukan 3 tahun yang lalu.

Laporan CAO - Bank Dunia menyebutkan bahwa tambang yang direncanakan oleh PT DPM akan sangat beresiko, ini jelas membahayakan jiwa kami, lingkungan, mata pencaharian dan kehidupan sosial kami ke depan.

Penjelasan lain dalam laporan CAO bahwa bendungan limbah PT DPM memiliki kombinasi resiko yang tinggi karena curah hujan tinggi, ketinggian bendungan, berada di lokasi hulu desa, akan menyebabkan kerusakan bendungan limbah dan potensi tercemar pada sumber air masyarakat yang sangat tinggi

Source: (Change.org, 2022)

Another petition, titled "Stop Deceit in the Name of Conservation, Reject Development in Komodo National Park!" also provides information on the environmental challenges facing Komodo National Park (TN) in NTT. The narrative and details presented by Chilia Dewi and the Forum Masyarakat Penyelamat Pariwisata Manggarai Barat (FORMAPP) are comprehensive in explaining why the conservation efforts in Komodo National Park should be halted. The investment plans of PT Segara Komodo Lestari and PT Komodo Wildlife Ecotourism in conservation areas and core zones could potentially impact the Komodo ecosystem. The justifications for the petition are further elucidated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Petition Information "Stop Deception in the Name of Conservation, Reject Development in Komodo National Park!" on Change.org Website

Berikut alasan-alasan mengapa kami **MENOLAK PEMBANGUNAN DI TN KOMODO:**

- 1. Penguasaan (pengelolaan) pihak swasta ada di titik-titik strategis dalam kawasan TN Komodo tidak membawa manfaat bagi masyarakat setempat.** Justru adanya tipu daya dengan pencaplokan sumber daya publik dan privatisasi (pengklaiman perseorangan) atas lahan dalam kawasan TN Komodo.
- 2. Kehadiran pihak swasta akan membebani masyarakat dalam kawasan dan menghambat para pelaku usaha wisata lokal.**
- 3. Bangunan fisik seperti villa, homestay dan tempat publik lainnya dalam kawasan TN Komodo akan berdampak buruk pada kelestarian TN Komodo.** Ruang hidup satwa komodo akan terganggu. Eksosistem juga akan rusak.
- 4. Dengan adanya bangunan-bangunan tersebut, sampah yang dihasilkan akan semakin banyak dan mencemari kawasan TN Komodo.**
- 5. Kebijakan dan regulasi tidak berpihak pada masyarakat dalam kawasan TN Komodo.**
- 6. Menghindari masuknya pihak swasta (investor) lain untuk mengelola kawasan konservasi TN Komodo.** Jika pembangunan ini terjadi, bukan tak mungkin pihak swasta lain akan berbondong-bondong merebut akses dan meraup keuntungan di TN Komodo.

Source: (Change.org, 2018b)

However, the authors also note that the Change.org petition website provides a forum for people to discuss the environmental issues addressed in the petition. The public can voice their opinions on the environmental concerns under discussion. Similarly, with the input provided after agreeing or signing the petition, the public can express their views on why environmental harm

must be halted. On the following page, you will find a description and samples of public discourse on Change.org petitions (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Public Dialogue on the Issue of Indonesian Environmental Destruction through Change.org Petition

Source: Change.org (2018b, 2022)

Based on the preceding discussion's outcomes, the authors conclude that the implementation and ramifications of digital democracy, in this example, digital community engagement utilizing digital petitions, are significant (information and dialog stages). It gives a forum for individuals to express their views, particularly their desires to conserve the environment in Indonesia. Therefore, the author contends that the emergence of e-petitions and Change.org in terms of information and dialogue can promote Indonesia's existing democracy.

3. Monitoring & Decision-Making Petition

There are several techniques to determine whether a petition has advanced or succeeded, but the simplest method is to apply digital and media monitoring to observe and develop the petition. This digital monitoring and media monitoring technique is carried out by watching the Change.org petition site and the petition's progress in relation to ecological politics and environmental protection. In addition, academics track petitions by measuring the petition process,

petition success (Victory), and petition efficacy. As described in the research methodology, 100 petitions were separated into three groups, and trends from 2022 to 2015 were examined. To track the Change.org petition generation process, this study subsequently created a table from the 100 petitions based on three groups.

Table 4. Total Petition Share

Rejection	Management	Protection
Successful Petition: 4	Petition Successful: 0	Successful Petition: 2
Petitions in Process: 18	Petition Process: 7	Petitions in Process: 9
Petitions Not Working: 34	Petitions Not Working: 10	Petitions Not Working: 16
Total Petitions: 56	Total Petitions: 17	Total Petitions: 27

Source: Collected and Proceed by the Authors

The authors discovered six effective and winning petitions out of a total of one hundred regarding ecological politics and the defense of the environment. After monitoring the six successful petitions in narrative style, this study dug up the petition's most recent information (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Petition Success in the Rejection Cluster

Source: (Change.org, 2018b)

The success of the petition is evidence of its influence on policymaking (Figure 7). This research monitored and discovered three successful petitions in the rejection cluster. The petition demonstrated the urgency of the problem of rejecting development because the existence of development would diminish the quality of life in the community. The petition also identified key figures and official institutions, such as Ministry Institutions, Courts, and even the President, to win support for the petition. Similarly, the petition to dismiss the environmentalists' complaint was granted by disclosing corruption cases that resulted in state losses.

For example, the victory of the petition against mining on Sanghie island was informed by Mongabay.co.id (2023). The Supreme Court rejected the cassation of production and operation licenses from the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources and PT Tambang Mas Sanghie (Sawal, 2023). Then, the victory of the petition about canceling the reclamation of Island G was reported by two online media such as liputan6.com Government Stops Island G Reclamation (Deny, 2016), from BBC News Indonesia PTUN Revokes Reclamation Permit for Three Islands in Jakarta Bay (BBC News Indonesia, 2017).

Figure 7. Petition Success in the Protection Cluster

Source: (Change.org, 2018b)

The National Committee for Agrarian Reform launched the first petition, which was initiated on July 18, 2019, to encourage the House of Representatives to reconsider the Land Bill. On December 20, 2019, in response to 222,116 signatures, the administration asked members of the House of Representatives to delay and cancel the Land Bill. The latest petition for the protection of animal habitats was posted on July 19, 2016, and is titled Release the Turtles and Sharks, now! The petition was sent to the Banyuwangi Environment Agency with the request that

they promptly decide to free the animals. On July 26, 2016, the petition lasted barely a week and was confirmed with 4,834 supporters, resulting in victory.

After analyzing the petition's success narratively, this study built a map by monitoring five indications of the petition's success. The influence and effect of a petition can vary, as can its effectiveness. In the accompanying table, the authors give the mapping of effectiveness metrics for ecological political petitions in safeguarding the environment.

Table 5. Monitoring Petition Effectiveness

Petition	Petition Effectiveness Indicator				
<i>Sanghie Pulau Indah, Kami Tolak Tambang (2021)</i>					
<i>Stop Danai PLTU Baru Indramayu, PLTU Bukan Untuk Masyarakat (2020)</i>					
<i>Tolak Gugatan Terhadap Basuki Wasis Pejuang Lingkungan (2018)</i>	Increased Signatures	Media Interaction	Public Support and Public Awareness	Authorities' Response	Policy Change
<i>Batalkan SK Reklamasi Pulau G Demi Nelayan (2016)</i>					
<i>Tinjau Ulang Rancangan Undang – Undang Belum Layak Untuk Di Sahkan (2019)</i>					
<i>Lepaskan Penyu dan Hiu, Sekarang (2016)</i>					

Source: Collected and Analyzed by the Authors

From six petition achievements, the authors may quantify it using five indications, such as the number of additional signatures that resulted in the petition's victory; the petition's efficacy can be determined by media coverage and public attention. Because it has influence and authority, the most significant factor is also the response from the authorities, so that public support and knowledge become support in establishing policy. Finally, policy change assesses the success of the petition by analyzing the requested modifications.

Likewise, the results of petitions created by the public to criticize government policies that have the potential to damage the environment also change a government policy, for example in the case of a petition created by the National Agrarian Committee, the petition began on July 18, 2019, to urge the House of Representatives to review the Land Law with the results of 222,116 signatories on December 20, 2019, the government asked members of the House of Representatives to cancel the Draft Law.

The announced successes demonstrate that digital petitions may alter politics, as evidenced by the above data and discussion outcomes. Until now, however, digital petitions or e-petitions have represented the notion that anybody may create online petitions. Simultaneously, the Change.org petition has evolved from a mere protest into a social movement. It is crucial to remember that while petitions can effectively campaign for critical sociopolitical concerns, they can also serve as a means of attracting attention to an issue to impact genuine change.

CONCLUSION

All in all, this study examines the effectiveness of online petitions in influencing legislation or policy changes due to social media interactions over the past ten years through the Change.org channel—a platform for campaigning on various social concerns. This study collects data from Change.org regarding ecological politics in defense of the environment. On Change.org, 100 petitions related to the politics of safeguarding the environment were identified. Researchers then categorized these 100 petitions into three clusters: rejection, management, and preservation. After segregating the three groups, the researchers analyzed four indicators: the Information Petition, the Dialogue Petition, the Monitoring Petition, and the Decision-Making Petition.

The findings of this study demonstrate that in information and dialogue, the implementation, and implications of digital democracy—in this case, digital community participation using digital petitions (information and dialogue stages)—do provide a forum for citizens to express their opinions, particularly their desires to protect the environment in Indonesia. After monitoring and decision-making, researchers assess the petition's effectiveness by considering media coverage, public attention, support, and awareness. The petition's influence and authority are evident through these factors. An essential element is also the authorities' response, making the petition a significant factor in policy formation.

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